

Cost-effectiveness of brief structured interventions to discontinue long-term benzodiazepine use: an economic analysis alongside a randomised controlled trial. Trepel D, Ali S, Gilbody S, Leiva A, Mcmillan D, Bejarano F, Sempere E and Vicens C

Supplemental 2: Costs associated with providing training workshops

Spanish Region	Balearic	Catalunya	Valencia
Workshops			
Number of workshops provided (WS)	3	2	3
No. Attendees (WS1)	11	14	6
No. Attendees (WS2)	10	13	7
No. Attendees (WS3)	6	-	8
Subtotal	27	27	21
Total receiving training for SIW	9	9	6
Total receiving training for SIF	9	8	9
Total receiving training for TAU	9	11	5
Trainer:			
Trainer profession	GP	GP	GP
Trainer per workshops	2	2	2
Unit cost per hour per trainer (Trainer profession)	75	75	75
Workshop Length for SIW (hours)	2	2	2
Workshop Length for SIF (hours)	2.5	2.5	2.5
Administration per workshop [exclude 1 hour of Unit cost per Hour (Administrative)]	2	2	2
Accommodation & Travel cost per workshop	275	275	275
Total cost of Accommodation & Travel per region	275	550	825
Total cost of Accommodation & Travel per GP	15.28	34.38	55
Miscellaneous Costs			
Venue Hire	0	0	0
Training material per GP attendee	€ 2	€ 2	€ 2
Organising attendance	0	0	0
GP Travel to training	0	0	0
Mean Total Cost per:			
Cost per SIW workshop	€ 468	€ 466	€ 462
Cost per SIF workshop	€ 543	€ 541	€ 543
Region receiving training (incl. travel costs)	1791.5	1557	2332.5
GP Attending SIW	€ 93	€ 93	€ 171
GP Attending SIF	€ 105.78	€ 102.00	€ 145.50
Patients (SIW+SIF at baseline)	€14.33	€13.42	€19.77